

EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES WITH TWO-DIMENSIONAL TUNGSTEN DISULFIDE ADDITIVES

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ABSTRACT

Two-dimensional materials can give composites many unique properties, such as mechanical, thermal, optical, electronic and magnetic properties. Besides the hottest two-dimensional materials, the graphene, some metal chalcogenides also have the layered structure, including tungsten disulfide. We chose the tungsten disulfide with nanosheet structure as a reinforcement for the resin matrix. Ultrasonication can make bulk tungsten disulfide into nanosheets, and disperse homogeneously in the solution. The nano structure were observed with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM). Then the nano tungsten disulfide was added to the epoxy resin to make reinforcement composites. Heat can remove the solvent, and through high speed agitation the nano tungsten disulfide was dispersed homogeneously in the resin matrix, forming the nano tungsten disulfide reinforced composite. The basic parameters, including the Vickers-hardness and the glass transition temperature (T_g) were measured to represent the mechanical properties. Crack-opening tests was conducted on both epoxy resin and nano tungsten disulfide to measure how the Mode I fracture toughness (K_{IC}) was affected. We changed the content of tungsten disulfide to see the effects on the composite. The results showed that the tungsten disulfide was a significant reinforcement for epoxy resin, especially for the enhancement of fracture toughness property, indicating a huge potential in the field of nanosheet composite materials.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer-based composite is a new kind of engineering materials. Compared with metal, polymer matrix has higher specific strength, higher specific stiffness, excellent electrical insulating property, chemical stability and good workability. So it is widely used in the aerospace field, military field and industrial manufacture.

Epoxy resin has excellent mechanical properties, electrical insulating property and chemical stability. But since pure epoxy has a relatively high cross linking degree after curing, it is brittle and easy-cracked. So it is necessary to improving the toughness of epoxy resins. There are lots of methods of toughening epoxy resins, including adding flexible-block-curing, introducing core-shell structure polymers, introducing thermotropic liquid crystalline polymers, forming interpenetrating polymer networks and adding nanofillers. Among these methods, adding nanofillers is the most attractive one because the additions can be variegated and it is easy to operate. Besides, by adding variety of functional additions, the character of the epoxy matrix can also be changed.

Tungsten disulphide (WS₂)[1] is a typical two-dimensional nanofiller. It is a kind of transition metal dichalcogenides and has similar characteristics of molybdenum disulphide (MoS₂)[2, 3]. Tungsten disulphide is a high band gap semiconductor and will not impart electrical conductivity to the polymer matrix[4] while at the same time potentially improving mechanical properties, especially the toughness. The two-dimensional structure offers tungsten disulphide excellent lubricating property. Besides, it also gives an possibility that it can be a good toughening additive to the traditional polymers, especially to brittle polymers such as epoxy resin[5, 6]. Eksis, et al.[7] have reported to add MoS₂ nanoplatelets (MNP) into epoxy, and the additives proved to be effective in improving the mechanical properties of epoxy composite at low nanofiller loadings. In this study, the bulk tungsten disulphide is exfoliated into nanoplatelets through ultrasonic dispersion in certain solvent. The nano structure were observed with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Then it is dispersed in epoxy resin with a weight fraction ranging from 0.1% to

0.5%. The glass-transition temperature, hardness and fracture properties were measured. The results show that tungsten disulphide nanoplatelets is an effective reinforcing additive for epoxy matrix at a low loading fraction.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Exfoliation of bulk WS₂

WS₂ (Changsha Huajing Powder Material Science & technology Co. LTD, 99.9%, 0.9 μ m), N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (Xilong Chemical Co. LTD, 99.0%), acetone (Beijing Chemical Works, 99.5%) were used in the experiment. Three methods were used to exfoliate the bulk WS₂: (1) The bulk WS₂ powder was sonicated in NMP for 6 hours, the sample was taken every 10 minutes. Then the mixture was centrifuged at 8000rpm for 10 minutes. Both the supernatant and the sediment were taken for the test. (2) The bulk WS₂ powder was sonicated in acetone with the similar processing as in (1). (3) The bulk WS₂ powder was treated with the same processing as (1), then the sediment was washed twice with acetone.

2.2 The preparation of the resin casting

Epoxy resin E-51 (epoxy value: 0.48-0.54, Bluestar New Chemical Materials Co. Ltd. Wuxi Resin Factory) and the triethylenetetramine (Xilong Chemical Co. LTD, 95%) was used. The layered WS₂ powder was sonicated for 30 minutes in acetone at a concentration of 2 mg/ml. Then mixture the solution of WS₂ and the epoxy resin. The acetone was then removed by rotary evaporation. The resin and curing agent was then mixed together and then cured at 60 $^{\circ}$ C for 2 hours and 80 $^{\circ}$ C for 1 hour.

2.3 Chemical physical characterization

The WS₂ nanoplatelets were observed via a field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) system (JOEL JSM-7500F) and a transmission electron microscope system (JEM-2100). The atomic force microscopy (Bruker's Dimension Icon) was used to see the thickness of the nanoplatelets. The differential scanning calorimeter (Star System) was used to measure the glass transition temperature of the WS₂/epoxy composite. The microhardness tester (FM-800) was used to measure the Vickers-hardness of the composite.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Exfoliation and dispersion of bulk WS₂

There are several methods to synthesize the WS₂ nanoplatelets: the bottom-up synthesis by chemical vapor deposition[8], lithium ion intercalation[2, 9], mechanical force exfoliation and ultrasonic exfoliation[10]. Among them, ultrasonic exfoliation is one of the most easily-operated one. Since we need a large amount of WS₂ nanoplatelets as nano additives, it is more cost-effective and time-saving to choose ultrasonic exfoliation method. Coleman. et al.[11] reported that solvents with surface tension close to γ -40 mJ/m² have better exfoliation effects, and Yuan. et al.[10] reported N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) with a surface tension of 41.0 mJ/m² is an effective solvent for WS₂ exfoliation. So we choose NMP as the solvent. The ultrasound time ranges from 30 minutes to six hours, and samples were taken every 30 minutes. Then the solution was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes and the supernatant was separated from the sediment. The original mixture was dark gray, while the supernatant of the mixture turns yellowish-green when the ultrasound time is beyond 2 hours, but up to six hours, the color doesn't change much (figure 1).

Figure 1 The supernatant of WS₂/NMP mixture after 2-6 hours' ultrasonic treatment and centrifugation

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were used to observe the nano structure of the supernatant and the sediment. The results suggest that both supernatant and sediment contain the WS₂ nanoplatelets, but the platelets in the sediment has a larger average size and they tend to be more agglomerations while the supernatant is opposite. Figure 2d shows a typical SEM image of WS₂ nanoplatelets in the sediment, which indicates that the bulk WS₂ can be exfoliated into platelets through 2 hours' ultrasonic treatment. The TEM image in figure 2e also shows the layer-structure of WS₂ nanoplatelets. The AFM image in figure 2a-c indicate the size of nanoplatelets is about several hundred nanometers and the thickness is about 5 nm. Since the single layer WS₂ is about 1nm in thickness, the nanoplatelets synthesized by above methods is expected to be 5-10 layers.

Figure 2 (a-c) The AFM image of WS₂/NMP sediment after 2 hours' ultrasonic treatment and

centrifugation. (d) The SEM image of WS₂/NMP sediment after 2 hours' ultrasonic treatment and centrifugation. (e) The TEM image of WS₂/NMP sediment after 2 hours' ultrasonic treatment and centrifugation.

Though NMP is an effective solvent for exfoliation, it has a relatively high boiling point of 204 °C. That indicates it is hard to separate the NMP from the mixture of WS₂ and the epoxy matrix. If the solvent is not totally removed from the epoxy, it will affect the mechanical properties of the sample. So we then tried acetone as the solvent, which has a boiling point of 56 °C and is commonly used in the epoxy composite. The same method was operated on the mixture of acetone and bulk WS₂. Even after six hours' ultrasonic treatment, the bulk WS₂ still exists as particles. The AFM image and SEM image in figure 3 shows the WS₂ in the acetone after 4 hours' ultrasonic treatment, which indicate the acetone is not effective enough to exfoliate the bulk WS₂.

Figure 3 (a-c) The AFM image of WS₂/NMP sediment after 4 hours' ultrasonic treatment and centrifugation. (d) The SEM image of WS₂/NMP sediment after 4 hours' ultrasonic treatment and centrifugation.

Since it is necessary to find a method to disperse the layered WS₂ in the epoxy matrix, the third method is used that we used the NMP as the solvent for ultrasound and then replace the NMP by acetone. After 10 minutes' centrifugation, the sediment is washed by acetone for 2 times. Figure 4d-e shows the SEM image and the TEM image of WS₂ washed by acetone, which indicate the WS₂ remains nanoplatelet-structure after washing. The AFM image in figure 4a-c shows the size of the nanoplatelets is about 200nm and the thickness is about 15nm, which is smaller and thicker than the sediment in NMP. This suggests the WS₂ nanoplatelets in acetone has more agglomerations.

Figure 4 (a-c) The AFM image of WS₂/NMP sediment after 2 hours' ultrasonic treatment, centrifugation and acetone washing. (d) The SEM image of WS₂/NMP sediment after 2 hours' ultrasonic treatment, centrifugation and acetone washing. (e) The TEM image of WS₂/NMP sediment after 2 hours' ultrasonic treatment, centrifugation and acetone washing.

3.2 Mechanical properties

The Vickers-hardness of WS₂/epoxy composite was measured. Figure 5 shows the Vickers-hardness of WS₂/epoxy composite with different WS₂ weight fraction. The result indicates the composite has a highest hardness at the loading of 0.2%, and as the weight fraction increases beyond 0.2%, the hardness decreases. When the loading of WS₂ is beyond 0.3%, the hardness is even lower than the epoxy matrix.

Figure 5 The Vickers-hardness of WS₂/epoxy composite with the WS₂ weight fraction ranging from 0 to 0.5%.

The glass transition temperature (T_g) is also affected by the addition of WS_2 . The differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to investigate the changing tendency of the composite. Figure 6 shows the T_g of WS_2 /epoxy composite with the WS_2 weight fraction ranging from 0 to 0.5%. The result shows the T_g increases from $78.58^\circ C$ of epoxy matrix to $123.65^\circ C$ at the WS_2 loading of 0.4 wt%. T_g shows the point when the polymer chain motion significantly increases, so the T_g changing suggests that the chain mobility is decreased by the low weight fraction addition of WS_2 . When the addition of WS_2 increases, the additives tend to get together and cannot disperse evenly, so the polymer chain tend to move more easily.

Figure 6 The T_g of WS_2 /epoxy composite with the WS_2 weight fraction ranging from 0 to 0.5%.

Figure 7 shows the impact strength of WS_2 /epoxy composite. The result demonstrates while the loading fraction of WS_2 ranges from 0.1% to 0.5%, the impact strength first increases and then decreases. This is possibly because when the loading fraction of WS_2 is low, the WS_2 layer is a reinforcement of the epoxy matrix. But as the loading fraction increases, the WS_2 filler begins to agglomerate and become defects of the matrix.

Figure 7 The impact strength of WS₂/epoxy composite with the WS₂ weight fraction ranging from 0 to 0.5%.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The bulk tungsten disulphide powder has the layered-structure and is able to be exfoliated through sonicating in NMP. After replace the NMP with acetone, the WS₂ remains its fewer-layers structure. The WS₂ powder is proved an effective reinforcement additive for epoxy resin at low weight fraction. Both the glass transition temperature and the Vickers-hardness increased after the addition of WS₂ powder. The Vickers-hardness of WS₂/epoxy composite increases 4.1% at 0.2 wt% WS₂ loading, and the Tg of WS₂/epoxy composite increases from 78.58 °C to 123.65 °C. The impact strength of the composite increases from 6.93 KJ/m² to 26.84 KJ/m². These results all indicate that WS₂ is a significant addition to epoxy resin.

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